

Synthesis and Characterisation of Uranium–Molybdenum Dithiocarbamate Complexes

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In this paper we report the synthesis and characterisation of uranium–molybdenum mixed metal complexes with dithiocarbamates. Such complexes may serve as models for molybdo-enzymes.

Experimental

Uranyl nitrate hexahydrate and sodium molybdate of A.R. grade were used as such. Sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate and piperidine dithiocarbamate were synthesised by standard methods¹. Uranyl molybdate was prepared by treating equimolar solutions of uranyl nitrate hexahydrate and sodium molybdate. The precipitated yellow compound was filtered and dried.

Preparation of mixed metal U–Mo complexes: Uranyl molybdate (0.5 g) was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml) mixed with DMF (10 ml) and the solution was cooled to 5°. Sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate (2.5 g) dissolved in water (50 ml) was cooled and added slowly to uranyl molybdate solution with stirring. The resulting purple coloured complex was washed with water and dried under reduced pressure. Piperidine dithiocarbamate complex was also prepared similarly.

Purity of the sample was determined by tlc using silica gel as the stationary phase and aqueous 85% acetonitrile as the mobile phase. Uranium and molybdenum were estimated as their oxinates². Sulphur was analysed by the conventional method. The magnetic moment, electronic, ir, far-ir and epr spectra were explored to elucidate structures of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

The presence of a single spot in the tlc studies of uranyl molybdenum diethyl dithiocarbamate (1) and uranyl molybdenum piperidine dithiocarbamate (2) complexes with R_f values of 0.92 and 0.90 respectively, indicated the discrete nature of these complexes. The analytical and spectral data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The elemental analyses correspond to the composition $UMoO_2L_6$, where L stands for diethyl dithiocarbamate or piperidine dithiocarbamate.

Electronic spectra ($CHCl_3$) of the complexes showed four bands at 260, 380, 630 and 760 nm.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		S	U	Mo
1	$UMoO_2(C_6H_{10}NS_2)_6$	30.69	19.10	7.53
		(30.79)	(18.99)	(7.65)
2	$UMoO_2(C_6H_{10}NS_2)_6$	29.05	18.12	7.30
		(28.98)	(17.93)	(7.23)

A strong band around 260 nm has been reported for the ligand transition³. The moderately strong band at 380 nm is due to the charge transfer transitions of sulphur to molybdenum⁴. A similar transition was observed earlier for iron–molybdenum dithiocarbamate complexes⁴. However, spectrum of uranium dithiocarbamate complex also gave a band at 380 nm due to the $S(\pi) \rightarrow U(f)$ charge transfer transition⁵. Thus the above mentioned band is probably a combination of the twin sulphur to metal transitions. The two latter absorptions were assigned to the $d \rightarrow d$ and $f \rightarrow f$ transitions of the metals, which is in good agreement with the earlier reports^{4,5} for molybdenum(v) and uranium(v) complexes.

The ir spectra (KBr) of the complexes exhibited a strong absorption at about 1490 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of the polar C=N moiety⁶ and a shoulder at 1510 cm^{-1} due to the binding of ligands to two different metal centres. ν_{C-S} for the dithiocarbamate ligand was observed at 1000 cm^{-1} , and due to complex formation this band was lowered by 10 and 30 cm^{-1} for 1 and 2 respectively. The peaks around 930 cm^{-1} were probably due to the ν_{C-S} of the bridging ligands. The Mo–O vibrations were observed⁷ at 915 and 890 cm^{-1} for 1 and 2 respectively. The U=O stretching vibration⁸ was at about 880 cm^{-1} for both the complexes.

Polyethylene supported far-ir spectra showed a strong broad band at about 490 cm^{-1} due to ν_{Mo-S} vibrations⁹, i.e. both the terminal and bridging ligands contributed towards the widening of the band. A similar band at about 430 cm^{-1} may be assigned¹⁰ to the total U–S stretching vibrations. Another strong band at 250 cm^{-1} could be due to the UO^{2+} moiety present in the complexes.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of 2.68 and 2.63 B.M. for the complexes 1 and 2 respectively, indicate the presence of two unpaired electrons. The epr spectra (Fig. 1) of the complexes both in powder and in $CHCl_3$ medium yield a single signal with well-resolved hyperfine splittings. The signal was split into only eight components due to the partial merging of the constituents. The g_{av} value (1.97) was the same for both the complexes in $CHCl_3$ solution as well as in solid phase. Thus from the magnetic and spectral studies we conclude that both the metals are in their +5 oxidation state.

Fig. 1. Epr spectrum of compound 1.

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